

PARTICIPATION TERMS AND CONDITIONS
OA Book Usage Data Trust and the OAEBUDT International Data Space
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Welcome to the OAEBUDT International Data Space (the “**OAEBUDT-IDS**”) governed by the Open Access (OA) Book Usage Data Trust (“**OAEBUDT**”) and the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office (Coordinating Office). These terms and conditions, together with any other documents they expressly incorporate by reference (collectively, “**Terms and Conditions**”), are effective as of the date of acceptance by and between the Participant (hereinafter, a “**Participant**” or “**you**”) that has been approved by OAEBUDT and the Open Scholarly Communication in the European Area for Scholarly Communication (“**OPERAS**”), a Belgian international not-for-profit association (AISBL) incorporated under the laws of Belgium, acting as the OAEBUDT fiscal host. The following Terms and Conditions govern your access to, participation in, and use of the information and services in the OAEBUDT-IDS.

YOU (A) ACKNOWLEDGE THAT YOU HAVE READ AND UNDERSTAND THESE TERMS AND CONDITIONS; (B) REPRESENT AND WARRANT THAT YOU HAVE THE RIGHT, POWER, AND AUTHORITY TO ENTER INTO THESE TERMS AND CONDITIONS; AND (C) ACCEPT THESE TERMS AND CONDITIONS AND AGREE THAT YOU ARE LEGALLY BOUND BY ITS TERMS.

PLEASE READ THESE TERMS AND CONDITIONS CAREFULLY BEFORE PARTICIPATING IN THE OAEBUDT-IDS, AS THEY CONTAIN IMPORTANT INFORMATION REGARDING YOUR LEGAL RIGHTS, REMEDIES AND OBLIGATIONS. THESE INCLUDE VARIOUS LIMITATIONS AND EXCLUSIONS.

THESE TERMS AND CONDITIONS ARE DEEMED ACCEPTED AND TAKE EFFECT UPON SIGNATURE OR BY ACCESSING AND USING THE OAEBUDT-IDS.

As a condition of participation in the Data Space, you acknowledge and agree that you may be presented with additional terms or agreements (collectively, “Additional Agreements”), in which case, such Additional Agreements collectively form part of and are incorporated into these Terms and Conditions. You may be participating in the OAEBUDT-IDS as a provider or licensor of certain data and information (hereinafter, a “**Data Provider**”), or as a recipient of certain data and information from the OAEBUDT-IDS (hereinafter, a “**Data Recipient**”). In any case, the Terms and Conditions shall apply respective of your participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS.

1. Definitions.

Any capitalized terms in these Terms and Conditions not defined herein shall have the meaning provided by the *Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS)* (the “**Rulebook**”) available at [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163158>] and as may be amended from time-to-time thereafter. For purposes of these Terms and Conditions, the following terms shall have the meaning ascribed to them below:

- a) “**Bulk Scraping or Harvesting**” means the process of using automated software to extract large quantities of data from the OAEBUDT-IDS at once.
- b) “**Controller**” shall have the same meaning as set forth in Article 4(7) of the GDPR.
- c) “**Coordinating Office**” means the OAEBUDT Coordinating Office hosted by OPERAS.
- d) “**Data Protection Laws**” means all applicable international, European, national, federal, state, and local laws and regulations relating to data privacy and data security or imposing requirements or restrictions related to the Processing of Personal Data, including the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016) and the United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation and amended Data Protection Act 2018 (collectively, the “GDPR”), United States data breach laws, and all other emerging privacy regulations in any jurisdiction implicated by these Terms and Conditions and the OAEBUDT-IDS.
- e) “**Data Subject**” shall have the same meaning as set forth in Article 4(1) of the GDPR.
- f) “**Law**” means (i) each applicable treaty, statute, law, rule, regulation, observation, or order by any governmental body and each judgment, injunction, order, writ, decree or award of any governmental body, and (ii) each obligation imposed by self-regulatory bodies promulgating standards that apply to a Participant.
- g) “**Personal Data**” shall have the same meaning as set forth in Article 4(1) of the GDPR.

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- h) **“Processing”** (with **“Process,” “Processes,”** and **“Processed”**) shall have the same meaning as set forth in Article 4(2) of the GDPR, and in any case, shall mean, at a minimum, any operation or set of operations performed on Personal Data or sets of Personal Data, whether or not by automated means, such as access, collection, recording, retention, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, blocking erasure, or destruction.
- i) **“Provider Data”** means any data or information provided by a Data Provider as part of its participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS. Provider Data may include certain Personal Data.

2. Participant Roles and Responsibilities.

- a) **Data Provider Obligations for Provider Data.** Data Provider represents and warrants that for any Provider Data:
- i. the Data Provider is compliant with all relevant Laws;
 - ii. the Data Provider has obtained all licenses, consents, and permissions, provided all notices and disclosures, and otherwise has all rights, in each case as required under applicable Law, to share, transmit, or otherwise disclose to the Data Space all such Provider Data;
 - iii. the Data Provider has obtained and complied with any approvals and determinations by an applicable authority (e.g., Institutional Review Board) in connection with the collection and transfer of Provider Data in connection with participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS;
 - iv. the Data Provider has complied with all use restrictions and other requirements of any license, consent, permission, or other contract and any website Terms and Conditions, terms of service, or other terms governing Data Provider’s use, sharing, transmission, or disclosure of such Provider Data;
 - v. By submitting, transmitting or otherwise disclosing Provider Data, the Data Provider grants OAEBUDT and OPERAS a limited, revocable, worldwide, non-exclusive, royalty-free license, to use, copy, reproduce, process, adapt, modify, publish, transmit, display and distribute such Provider Data solely for the facilitation, operation, and on-going management of the OAEBUDT-IDS in accordance with these Terms and Conditions; and
 - vi. By authorising the submission, transmission or other disclosure of Provider Data, the Data Provider has and grants the Data Recipients all the necessary rights, title, and interests, in and to the Provider Data, as disclosed by the Data Provider.
- b) **Other Data Provider Obligations.** Data Provider further represents and warrants that:
- i. It shall establish that it maintains active responsibility and legal authority for the Provider Data; and
 - ii. It meets the requirements of Data Providers set forth in the Rulebook and associated participation terms, conditions, and legal agreements.
- c) **Data Recipient Obligations.**
- i. Data Recipient shall be responsible for making all arrangements necessary to have access to the OAEBUDT-IDS, and for ensuring that all persons who access the OAEBUDT-IDS are aware of these Terms and Conditions and comply with them.
 - ii. Data Recipient acknowledges and agrees that it may be asked to provide certain registration details or other information. It is a condition of Data Recipients’ use of the OAEBUDT-IDS that all the information provided in connection to the OAEBUDT-IDS is correct, current, and complete.
 - iii. Data Recipient agrees that all information provided to register with the OAEBUDT-IDS or otherwise, including, but not limited to, through the use of any interactive features on or in connection with the OAEBUDT-IDS, is governed by the OPERAS Privacy Policy [<https://operas-eu.org/privacy-policy/>].
- d) **General Rights and Obligations.**
- i. If a Participant or a user that is authorized, directly and/or indirectly, by a Participant to use the OAEBUDT-IDS (**“Authorized User”**) chooses or is provided with a username, password, or any other piece of information as part of the OPERAS security procedures (the **“User Credentials”**), a

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Participant and their Authorized User must treat such information as confidential, and must not disclose it to any other person or entity.

- ii. By participating in or accessing the OAEBUDT-IDS, a Participant and their Authorized Users must use their User Credentials, and any other security and identification methods as OPERAS may require from time to time, such as security questions or one-time passcodes, and you acknowledge and agree that this system includes security procedures that are commercially reasonable. A Participant and their Authorized Users must further agree to comply with any OPERAS procedures and processes to obtain any User Credentials, or to further access or use the OAEBUDT-IDS.
- iii. PARTICIPANT AND AUTHORIZED USERS AGREE TO NOTIFY OPERAS IMMEDIATELY OF ANY UNAUTHORIZED ACCESS TO OR USE OF ANY USER CREDENTIALS OR ANY OTHER BREACH OF SECURITY.

e) OAEBUDT Rights and Obligations.

- i. OAEBUDT reserves the right to modify, change, or otherwise amend the OAEBUDT-IDS in its sole discretion without notice. OPERAS will not be liable if, for any reason, all or any part of the OAEBUDT-IDS is unavailable at any time or for any period. From time to time, OPERAS may restrict access to some parts of the OAEBUDT-IDS.
- ii. Except for Provider Data, the OAEBUDT-IDS and its entire features and functionality (including but not limited to all information, software, text, displays, images, video, and audio, and the design, selection, and arrangement thereof) are managed by OPERAS and Think-IT on behalf of OAEBUDT, its licensors, or other providers of such material, and are protected by European, United States, and other international copyright, trademark, patent, trade secret, and other intellectual property or proprietary rights laws.
- iii. These Terms and Conditions permit the Participant's Authorized User(s) to access and use the OAEBUDT-IDS on behalf of the Participant, and only for specifically authorized business purposes. Participant and their Authorized Users must not reproduce, distribute, modify, create derivative works of, publicly display, publicly perform, republish, download, store or transmit any of the material on the OAEBUDT-IDS, except as explicitly permitted under these Terms and Conditions.

3. Data Exchange and Use.

- a) Participants agree to make transparent the Data Provenance, Data Processing and Stewardship, and Licensing for the Provider Data sent or received via the OAEBUDT-IDS as described in the relevant section of the Rulebook [Section II Part II] and these Terms and Conditions.
- b) The Coordinating Office will hold Participants accountable through a variety of mechanisms provided in the Rulebook [Section II Part IV]. As such, in accordance with the Rulebook, Participants agree to make the required disclosures for the transparency of the Data Provenance, Data Stewardship, and Licensing for the usage data sent or received via the OAEBUDT-IDS as described in the Rulebook and OAEBUDT-IDS Agreements.

4. OAEBUDT-IDS Usage Restrictions. OAEBUDT aims to foster the exchange of trusted data among trusted parties. To reinforce trust, Participants may not:

- a) access OAEBUDT-IDS or Provider Data except as expressly permitted by these Terms and Conditions and specific agreements executed directly between Data Providers and Data Recipients;
- b) reverse engineer, decompile or disassemble any OAEBUDT-IDS software or systems;
- c) Bulk Scrape or Harvest or otherwise bulk download data accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS unless expressly allowed by a specific Data Provider's terms and conditions;
- d) rent, lease, or assign access to the OAEBUDT-IDS;
- e) copy, analyze, publish, or in any way utilize the OAEBUDT-IDS Provider Data other than expressly authorized by these Terms and Conditions;

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- f) forward or pass along data outside of the OAEBUDT-IDS environment unless expressly permitted by the Rulebook, these Terms and Conditions, or the Data Provider's terms and conditions;
 - g) identify or re-identify unique individuals from masked or otherwise pseudonymized information accessed via the OAEBUDT-IDS;
 - h) transfer any rights under these Terms and Conditions to anyone else, including an affiliate, without the signed written consent of OAEBUDT, as applicable;
 - i) misrepresent one's identity or Participant affiliation when interacting with the OAEBUDT-IDS;
 - j) misrepresent the license applicable to the data or otherwise exceed the license limitations set by the Data Provider;
 - k) falsify, inflate, conceal, or otherwise intentionally misrepresent data exchanged by Participants on the OAEBUDT-IDS; or
 - l) permit any employees and/or agents to perform any of the activities listed above, and Participants agree to maintain reasonable safeguards to prevent others from performing any of the activities listed above.

Violations are a breach of these Terms and Conditions and will be subject to the accountability mechanisms provided in the latest published Rulebook [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11163157].

5. Ownership & Licenses.

- a) A Participant shall not have any right, title or interest in or to the OAEBUDT-IDS, which shall be the exclusive property of the OAEBUDT, as applicable, in all respects. All patents, copyrights, trademarks, trade secrets and other ownership rights in the OAEBUDT-IDS are and shall remain with the OAEBUDT, as applicable. As between the parties, all information regarding the design, structure or internal operation of the OAEBUDT-IDS are restricted as applicable.
- b) A Data Provider can only apply usage requirements, limitations, or licenses to data they make available via the Data Space if:
 - i. the Data Provider created the data and has full legal authority over such data; or
 - ii. the Data Provider certifies that they have obtained all licenses, consents, and permissions, provided all notices and disclosures, and otherwise has all rights, in each case as required under applicable Law, to share, transmit, or otherwise disclose to the OAEBUDT-IDS, all such Provider Data, and under the license(s) granted by the Data Provider (i.e., through an existing vendor contract or Open License).
- c) To receive data from a specific Data Provider via the OAEBUDT-IDS, a Data Recipient must:
 - i. have an existing legally binding agreement, license, or permission that authorizes access to the Data Provider's Provider Data through the OAEBUDT-IDS; and
 - ii. accept full responsibility and legal liability to manage, share, and use the Data Provider's Provider Data according to such terms.
- d) OAEBUDT grants the Participant and their Authorized Users a limited, revocable, worldwide right and license to use the OAEBUDT-IDS, solely in accordance with these Terms and Conditions and the Rulebook.

6. Issue Reporting, Investigation & Remedies.

- a) **Issue Reporting.**
 - i. Participants must report suspicious or incorrect data provided by Data Providers through the OAEBUDT-IDS, including suspicious Provider Data inconsistency.
 - ii. Participants may report suspected agreement noncompliance for any Participant or OAEBUDT-IDS service provider.
- b) **Investigations.**
 - i. OAEBUDT will investigate reports according to the procedure described in the Rulebook [Section II - Part IV]. Investigations and issue resolution processes may temporarily impact data connections.

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- ii. The Coordinating Office will notify the Data Provider(s) and/or Data Recipient(s) impacted and/or named within the received incident report and will provide full access to the submitted issue report. Depending on the severity and urgency of the issue, the Data Provider or Data Recipient subject of the issue investigation will have a set number of business days from the date of notification receipt to:
 1. acknowledge receipt of the notice (1 business day);
 2. conduct their internal investigation (varies depending on the issue); and
 3. develop and propose their issue resolution action plan as a response back to the Coordinating Office and reporting OAEBUDT-IDS Participant (varies depending on the issue but no more than 10 business days).
 - iii. If action cannot be taken by the subject of the issue investigation to fully remedy the issue within the specified number of business days, the Coordinating Office will suspend membership and Data Connectors related to the subject of the investigation until a plan of action is accepted and agreed upon. The OAEBUDT and OPERAS reserve the right at their sole discretion to engage legal counsel or law enforcement as necessary.
 - iv. The OAEBUDT will work in good faith with Data Providers and Data Recipients to address reported issues. However, if the evidence is found that provided data was intentionally misrepresented or that actions were taken in direct conflict with the Rulebook or these Terms and Conditions, the OAEBUDT and OPERAS reserve the right to take action in accordance with these Terms and Conditions.
 - v. Without limiting the foregoing, OAEBUDT and OPERAS have the right to cooperate fully with any law enforcement authorities or court order requesting or directing us to disclose the identity or other information of anyone posting any materials on or through the OAEBUDT-IDS. PARTICIPANTS WAIVE AND HOLD HARMLESS OAEBUDT, OPERAS AND THEIR PERSONNEL, LICENSEES, AND SERVICE PROVIDERS FROM ANY CLAIMS RESULTING FROM ANY ACTION TAKEN BY OAEBUDT, OPERAS OR ANY OF THE FOREGOING PARTIES DURING, OR TAKEN AS A CONSEQUENCE OF, INVESTIGATIONS BY EITHER OAEBUDT, OPERAS OR SUCH PARTIES OR LAW ENFORCEMENT AUTHORITIES.
 - vi. The OAEBUDT and OPERAS do not guarantee review of any material or Provider Data before it is posted on the OAEBUDT-IDS, and cannot ensure prompt removal of objectionable material after it has been posted. Accordingly, we assume no liability for any action or inaction regarding transmissions, communications, or content provided by any user or third party. We have no liability or responsibility to anyone for the performance or nonperformance of the activities described in this section.
- c) **Remedies.** Violations of these Terms and Conditions may result in the following, without limitation:
- i. temporarily or permanently disabling Data Connectors;
 - ii. temporary pause to data exchange via the OAEBUDT-IDS to or from the participating Participant in question, including IP address blocking;
 - iii. OAEBUDT member communications, such as an OAEBUDT-IDS notice to Data Recipients reflecting an active investigation or an OAEBUDT network-wide communication regarding the issue;
 - iv. moving an Active Member into probationary standing or terminating an Active Member;
 - v. legal action and liability; or
 - vi. expulsion from the OAEBUDT network and Data Space without financial refund or recourse.

The OAEBUDT and OPERAS may resolve an issue with or without a warning being noted on an Active Member's record.

7. **Audit of Access & Transmission.** The OAEBUDT may generate logs recording activities taken by Data Providers and Data Recipients within the OAEBUDT-IDS environment. Data Providers will have access to audit logs that exist for the data they make available via the OAEBUDT-IDS via Data Connectors. Data Recipients will have access to the audit logs that exist for their own activity. The Coordinating Office will have

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access to all audit logs, as well as OAEBUDT legal and technical service providers, such as Think-IT, on an as-needed basis.

8. Data Use and Transfer Agreements.

- a) the Data Provider and the Data Recipient, as the case may be, will comply with the Terms and Conditions set forth in their mutual applicable Data Use and Data Transfer Agreements.
- b) The Parties will cooperate and discuss in good faith any amendments or additional agreements that may be required in OAEBUDT or OPERAS's sole discretion in respect of any cross-border Processing of Personal Data, including but not limited to the execution of standard contractual clauses and/or other model contracts or data transfer agreements that may be required under applicable Data Protection Laws, and the respective jurisdictions of the Data Provider, Data Recipient, and/or Provider.
- c) Participant(s) shall provide information to OAEBUDT promptly upon request about the laws and regulations in the countries where Personal Data will be Processed and shall cooperate with OAEBUDT as reasonably requested in ensuring compliance with applicable requirements for cross-border transfers of Personal Data as established by Data Protection Laws and/or Regulators from time to time, including but not limited to implementing supplementary measures and/or additional safeguards with respect to the Personal Data.
- d) Each Participant and OAEBUDT acknowledge and agree to enter into additional agreements to the extent required by Data Protection Laws or other applicable Law, insofar as such agreements are required to operate, maintain, and participate in the Data Space and abide by all relevant Data Protection and other applicable laws.

9. Term & Termination.

- a) **Term.** Once accepted by both parties, these Terms and Conditions shall commence and remain in effect even upon termination of Membership either by OAEBUDT, OPERAS or a Participant.
- b) **Termination by OAEBUDT or OPERAS.** OAEBUDT may terminate membership at any time if (a) Participant fails to adhere to the Rulebook requirements, (b) Participant violates the Ownership or Confidentiality provisions of these Terms and Conditions, (c) Participant is no longer an Active Member, (d) Participant materially breaches these Terms and Conditions without having cured such breach within thirty (30) days following notice thereof, (e) Participant terminates a Data Space Agreement or (f) OAEBUDT elects to discontinue the Data Space, or international participation in the Data Space, for any reason.
- c) **Termination by Participant.** A Participant may terminate their participation in OAEBUDT-IDS at any time upon thirty (30) days' notice to OAEBUDT. Such notice shall be sent to [executivedirector\[at\]joabookusage.org](mailto:executivedirector@joabookusage.org) or such other notice address as may be provided to Participant by OAEBUDT or OPERAS from time to time.
- d) **Membership Fee:** Any kind of Membership termination will not result in any refund of fees paid.
- e) **Licensing Agreements:** Data received by Participants through the OAEBUDT-IDS under a specific license shall remain governed by the terms and conditions of that license, notwithstanding the termination of their participation.
- f) **Participant Personal Data Retention Period:** Data will be retained according to Belgian Law and the OPERAS policy on Personal Data Retention Period.

10. Confidentiality.

- a) Participant agrees to treat all information relating to the operation of the OAEBUDT-IDS that is disclosed to Participant under these Terms and Conditions, including the protocol (if applicable) and authorized persons' usernames and passwords, as confidential and in accordance with these Terms and Conditions.
- b) The Participant agrees to protect such information using the same degree of care with which they protect their own confidential information but in no event using less than reasonable care.
- c) Participants will not disclose, reveal or give such information to anyone except those who have a need to have such information, including an Institutional Review Board (as necessary), in connection with their

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participation in the OAEBUDT-IDS and who have assumed an obligation of confidentiality at least to the extent that Participant is bound hereunder.

- d) The preceding obligation of confidentiality will not apply to information that:
- i. can be demonstrated to have been in the public domain or publicly known and readily available prior to disclosure;
 - ii. can be demonstrated to have been in Participant's possession or readily available to Participant from another source, not subject to the terms of confidentiality, prior to the disclosure;
 - iii. becomes part of the public domain or publicly known by publication or otherwise, not due to any unauthorized act by Participant, or Participant's employees or agents;
 - iv. is independently developed or acquired by Participant without the use of or reliance upon the information provided by OAEBUDT; or
- e) is required to be disclosed by law, provided that Participant notifies OAEBUDT and OPERAS before the disclosure is made to allow OAEBUDT and OPERAS to seek the advice of counsel.

11. Independent Contractor.

- a) Participant and OAEBUDT agree that these Terms and Conditions are not intended to create, and do not establish, a partnership, joint venture, agency or other arrangement between or among the parties and that the relationship of the parties is that of independent contractors.
- b) No party, by virtue of these Terms and Conditions, shall have any right, power or authority, expressed or implied, to act on behalf of or enter into any undertaking binding another party.

12. Compliance with Laws. While participating in the OAEBUDT-IDS, Participant shall comply with all applicable international, European, federal, state and local rules and guidelines, including, but not limited to, the requirements of Data Protection Laws.

13. Disclaimer. You understand that OAEBUDT and OPERAS cannot and do not guarantee or warrant that any information or data available from the OAEBUDT-IDS will be operable, free of defects, viruses, or other contaminants, or that they will be fit for any particular purpose. You are responsible for implementing sufficient procedures and checkpoints to satisfy your particular requirements for anti-virus protection and accuracy of data input and output, and for maintaining a means external to the OAEBUDT-IDS for any reconstruction of any lost data.

TO THE FULLEST EXTENT PROVIDED BY LAW, OAEBUDT AND OPERAS WILL NOT BE LIABLE FOR ANY LOSS OR DAMAGE CAUSED BY A DISTRIBUTED DENIAL-OF-SERVICE ATTACK, VIRUSES, OR OTHER TECHNOLOGICALLY HARMFUL MATERIAL THAT MAY INFECT YOUR COMPUTER EQUIPMENT, COMPUTER PROGRAMS, DATA, OR OTHER PROPRIETARY MATERIAL DUE TO YOUR USE OF OR PARTICIPATION IN THE OAEBUDT-IDS, OR ANY SERVICES OR ITEMS OBTAINED THROUGH THE OAEBUDT-IDS OR TO YOUR DOWNLOADING OF ANY MATERIAL POSTED ON IT, OR ON ANY WEBSITE OR APP LINKED TO IT.

YOUR USE OF THE OAEBUDT-IDS, ITS CONTENT, AND ANY SERVICES OR ITEMS OBTAINED THROUGH THE OAEBUDT-IDS IS AT YOUR OWN RISK. THE OAEBUDT-IDS AND ANY SERVICES OR ITEMS OBTAINED THROUGH THE OAEBUDT-IDS ARE PROVIDED ON AN "AS IS" AND "AS AVAILABLE" BASIS, WITHOUT ANY WARRANTIES OF ANY KIND, EITHER EXPRESS OR IMPLIED, STATUTORY, OR OTHERWISE, INCLUDING BUT NOT LIMITED TO ANY WARRANTIES OF MERCHANTABILITY, NON-INFRINGEMENT, AND FITNESS FOR PARTICULAR PURPOSE. NEITHER OAEBUDT, OPERAS NOR ANY PERSON ASSOCIATED WITH OAEBUDT OR OPERAS MAKES ANY WARRANTY OR REPRESENTATION WITH RESPECT TO THE COMPLETENESS, SECURITY, RELIABILITY, QUALITY, ACCURACY, OR AVAILABILITY OF THE OAEBUDT-IDS. WITHOUT LIMITING THE FOREGOING, NEITHER OAEBUDT OR OPERAS NOR ANYONE ASSOCIATED WITH OAEBUDT OR OPERAS REPRESENTS OR WARRANTS THAT THE OAEBUDT-IDS, ITS CONTENT, ANY PROVIDER DATA, OR ANY SERVICES OR ITEMS OBTAINED THROUGH THE OAEBUDT-IDS WILL BE ACCURATE, RELIABLE, ERROR-FREE, OR UNINTERRUPTED, THAT DEFECTS WILL BE CORRECTED, THAT THE OAEBUDT

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WEBSITE(S) OR THE SERVER(S) THAT MAKE THE OAEBUDT-IDS AVAILABLE ARE FREE OF VIRUSES OR OTHER HARMFUL COMPONENTS, OR THAT THE OAEBUDT-IDS OR ANY SERVICES OR ITEMS OBTAINED THROUGH THE OAEBUDT-IDS WILL OTHERWISE MEET YOUR, OR YOUR PARTICIPANT'S NEEDS OR EXPECTATIONS.

THE FOREGOING DOES NOT AFFECT ANY WARRANTIES THAT CANNOT BE EXCLUDED OR LIMITED UNDER APPLICABLE LAW.

14. Limitation on Liability.

TO THE FULLEST EXTENT PROVIDED BY LAW, IN NO EVENT WILL OPERAS AND OAEBUDT, THEIR PERSONNEL, OR THEIR LICENSORS, SERVICE PROVIDERS, EMPLOYEES, AGENTS, OFFICERS, OR DIRECTORS BE LIABLE FOR DAMAGES OF ANY KIND, UNDER ANY LEGAL THEORY, ARISING OUT OF OR IN CONNECTION WITH YOUR USE, OR INABILITY TO USE, THE OAEBUDT-IDS, ANY PROVIDER DATA, ANY WEBSITE OR APPS LINKED TO IT, ANY CONTENT ON THE OAEBUDT-IDS, INCLUDING ANY DIRECT, INDIRECT, SPECIAL, INCIDENTAL, CONSEQUENTIAL, OR PUNITIVE DAMAGES, INCLUDING BUT NOT LIMITED TO, PERSONAL INJURY, PAIN AND SUFFERING, EMOTIONAL DISTRESS, LOSS OF REVENUE, LOSS OF PROFITS, LOSS OF BUSINESS OR ANTICIPATED SAVINGS, LOSS OF USE, LOSS OF GOODWILL, LOSS OF DATA, AND WHETHER CAUSED BY TORT (INCLUDING NEGLIGENCE), BREACH OF CONTRACT, OR OTHERWISE, EVEN IF FORESEEABLE.

The limitation of liability set out above does not apply to liability resulting from our gross negligence or willful misconduct.

THE FOREGOING DOES NOT AFFECT ANY LIABILITY THAT CANNOT BE EXCLUDED OR LIMITED UNDER APPLICABLE LAW.

15. Indemnification. You agree to defend, indemnify, and hold harmless OPERAS and OAEBUDT, their personnel, licensors, and service providers, and their respective officers, directors, employees, contractors, agents, licensors, suppliers, successors, and assigns from and against any claims, liabilities, damages, judgments, awards, losses, costs, expenses, or fees (including reasonable attorneys' fees) arising out of or relating to your violation of these Terms and Conditions or your use of the OAEBUDT-IDS, including, but not limited to, Provider Data, any use of the OAEBUDT-IDS's content, services, and products other than as expressly authorized in these Terms and Conditions, or your use of any information obtained from the OAEBUDT-IDS.

16. Governing Law and Jurisdiction. Unless otherwise prescribed by applicable law, the laws of Belgium (without giving effect to its conflict of laws principles) govern all matters arising out of or relating to these Terms and Conditions, including, without limitation, its interpretation, construction, performance and enforcement. The Parties further agree that any claim or dispute arising out of these Terms and Conditions shall be decided exclusively by a court competent jurisdiction located in Brussels, and neither Party will object to such jurisdiction or venue on the grounds of lack of personal jurisdiction, forum, inconvenient or otherwise. This Section shall not deprive you of the mandatory protections of the laws of the country where you are domiciled. Any proceedings will be conducted in English.

17. Entire Agreement. These Terms and Conditions, including all applicable schedules, constitute the entire agreement between or among the parties with respect to the subject matter contained herein and supersedes all previous oral or written negotiations, understandings or proposals and may be modified only by an agreement executed in writing by the authorized representatives of both parties. In the event of any inconsistency between these Terms and Conditions and any schedule, the terms of these Terms and Conditions shall govern.

18. Waiver. No term or provision of these Terms and Conditions shall be deemed waived or any breach excused unless such waiver or consent shall be in writing and signed by the party claimed by the other to have waived

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or consented. Any consent by any party to, or waiver of, a breach by the other, whether express or implied, shall not constitute a consent to, waiver of or excuse for any other different or subsequent breach.

19. Severability. The invalidity, illegality or unenforceability of any one or more of the provisions of these Terms and Conditions, including any schedule hereto, shall in no way affect or impair the validity, legality or enforceability of the remaining provisions hereof, which shall remain in full force and effect. Any invalid, illegal or unenforceable provisions shall be deemed to be severed from these Terms and Conditions.

20. Authorizations. Participant agrees that the signatory below is duly authorized to bind the named Participant to the terms and conditions of these Terms and Conditions and any schedules hereto.

OPERAS

{PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION}

SIGNATURE

SIGNATURE

DATE

DATE